

Frequency of myocardial bridging on CTCA and its relation with coronary plaques - A single center study

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ABSTRACT:

Purpose: To determine the frequency of myocardial muscle bridging on computerized tomography coronary angiography (CTCA), and to see if the segment proximal to the myocardial bridge is more prone to atherosclerotic plaque formation.

Materials and methods: A total of 2515 patients who had undergone CTCA at our institution between Jan 2024 and Dec 2024 were studied for myocardial bridging and atherosclerotic changes. **Results:** The frequency of myocardial bridging among patients undergoing CTCA was 15.7%. Prevalent gender was male and the mean age was 60.3 years. The usual segment involved was mid left anterior descending artery (LAD). The frequency of atherosclerotic plaques in coronary artery with bridged segment was 30.4%. **Conclusion:** The frequency of myocardial muscle bridging in our study population was 15.7% with mid-LAD being the most common segment involved. Moreover, there was no significant association of atherosclerotic coronary plaque formation in bridged coronary artery.

Keywords: CTCA, myocardial bridging, coronary plaque, LAD

INTRODUCTION:

A variable length of intramural course of an epicardial coronary artery is known as myocardial bridging. The bridge is the muscle that surrounds the tunneled vessel. If the patient's hemodynamics is not affected, myocardium bridging is not a concerning issue. Myocardial bridging becomes clinically significant when regional hemodynamics are compressed and later compromised [1]. Acute coronary syndromes [2-4], coronary spasm, ventricular arrhythmias, sudden cardiac death, and coronary atherosclerotic plaques proximal to the bridged segment [5-7] are among the clinical syndromes linked to myocardial bridging. The frequency of myocardial bridging varies greatly depending on the type of investigation, and even the gender distribution varies significantly, with some studies reporting an equal prevalence in both genders and others revealing a male or female propensity [8]. Conventional invasive angiography is the gold standard for diagnosis, but with the introduction of cardiac magnetic resonance imaging, multislice computed tomography (CT), and CT coronary angiography (CTCA), opinions regarding the best modality to use for identifying coronary anomalies, such

as myocardial bridging, have changed. This is because these newer modalities offer three-dimensional and multiplanar reformats that makes it easier to recognize coronary anomalies. With modern technology CT acquisition time is lowered and motion artifacts are reduced, hence, myocardial bridging can be detected more precisely. Still in most studies the occurrence of myocardial bridging on CTCA varies significantly from 3.5% to 58% [9-11].

The treatment of myocardial bridging has been controversial because of its clinical, hemodynamic, and prognostic implications, as evidenced by earlier researches; this is because few investigators believe that myocardial bridging is a benign condition with no significant consequences. Atherosclerosis has its own sequel that is connected to the course of treatment and clinical results [12]. At a high-throughput tertiary care facility, we investigated the CT frequency of myocardial bridging and its association with coronary plaques in the local population.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study population:

A total of 2515 individuals who had undergone CTCA for evaluation of chest pain syndromes at our institute from Jan 2024 to Dec2024 were studied for myocardial bridging. 200 of them were excluded due to suboptimal imaging secondary to patient characteristics like obesity and motion artifacts. Data from the hospital data base in patients with myocardial bridging was collected.

Multidetector computed tomography protocol:

Following intravenous iodinated contrast administration at the rate 1 ml/kg, CTCA was performed using 640-slice CT. This study only included participant with sinus rhythm. Oral metoprolol was administered an hour prior to the scan to lower the heart rate to less than 70 beats

per minute. Using typical parameters, such as detector collimation (64×0.625 mm), voltage (120 kVp), effective mAs (400-500 mAs), pitch range (0.2-2.29), gantry rotation time (0.35), and slice thickness (0.6 mm), ECG-gated images were acquired during breath holding.

Myocardial bridging and coronary plaques:

The presence of myocardial bridging was assessed using transverse images and curved multiplanar reconstructed images when a part of the epicardial coronary artery embeds within the myocardium and returns back to the surface, Fig 1.

A coronary plaque is any thickening of the vessel wall with or without narrowing of the lumen, and it is graded into normal, insignificant ($< 50\%$ narrowing), and significant ($> 50\%$ narrowing), Fig 1&4

FIGURE 1: Relationship of plaques with myocardial bridging

Pathophysiology:

A 'milking' phenomenon brought on by myocardial contraction may compress the bridging segment, potentially resulting in myocyte ischemia due to reduced perfusion, Fig 2.

FIGURE 2: Classification of myocardial bridging

RESULTS:

Out of 2315 patients, 365(15.7%) had muscle bridging. Of 365 patients with myocardial bridging 111 (30.4%) patients had atherosclerotic disease;605 (26%) patients had atherosclerotic plaques with no bridging; and 1345(58%) patients were entirely normal having no plaques and no bridging. The mean age of the patients was 60.3 years with a range of 30 to 80 years. Out of 365 patients, 100 were between 30-50years age bracket and 265 patients were between 50-80 years age bracket.200 were males and 165 were females. Male to female ratio 5:4.1.Mid LAD was most prevalent bridged segment (96%), 5 patients had bridging in LCx and RCA. In almost all cases, atherosclerotic plaques were observed proximal to bridge segment (28.7%), while only 6 cases had disease distal to the bridged segment (1.6%), Table 1, Graph 1.

The p-value to see association between presence of atherosclerotic plaques and muscle bridging was 0.81, which is not significant, Table 2.

TABLE 1: Distribution of different characteristics of the patients

CHARACTERISTICS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
AGE		
30-50YRS	100	27.3%
50-80YRS	265	72.6%
MEAN	60.3	
GENDER		
MALE	200	54.7%
FEMALE	165	45.2%
MYOCARDIAL MUSCLE BRIDGE		
PRESENT	365	15.7%
ABSENT	1950	84.2%
ARTERY AND SEGEMENT INVOLVED		
LAD	360	98.6%
MID	352	97.7%
DISTAL	8	2.2%
OTHERS	5	1.3%
PLAQUES IN RELATION TO BRIDGED SEGMENT		
NONE	254	69.5%
PROXIMAL	105	28.7%
DISTAL	6	1.6%

TABLE 2: Association of plaques with bridging

CHARACTERRISTIC	NO OF PTS	P-VALUE	SIGNIFICANCE
PROXIMAL AND DISTAL PLAQUES WITH BRIDGING	111	0.81	<0.05
BRIDGING WITH NO PLAQUES	254		
NO BRIDGING WITH PLAQUES	605		
NO BRIDGING NO PLAQUES	1345		

GRAPH 1: Overview of association of plaques with bridging

FIGURE 3: Computed tomography cardiac CT image

- A. Sagittal reformat showing normal epicardial course of distal LAD which entry and exit of bridged segment (arrow)**
- B. Orthogonal multiplanar reformat image showing muscle bridging**
- C. Curved multiplanar reformat image showing myocardial bridging of mid left anterior descending artery (LAD) (arrow). Volume rendered image showing myocardial bridging of mid LAD**
- D. Transverse image showing myocardial bridging of LAD (arrow)**

FIGURE 4: Curved multiplanar reformat image of MDCT showing myocardial bridging of mid left anterior descending artery (LAD) (red arrow) with proximal plaque (yellow arrow).

DISCUSSION:

In majority of studies, the frequency of myocardial bridging varies greatly, ranging from 0.5% to 19%. Based upon angiographic findings many studies have reported similar statistics [13].

The gender distribution was almost equal, which is consistent with what has been observed in prior researches [14]. Similarly, mid-LAD was the most common segment and LAD was the most common vessel involved in almost all studies [15, 16]. According to the blood flow dynamics, there is tangential stress on the endothelium, which is thought to be lower than normal for the bridged segment and higher for the proximal segment. This stress was linked to atherosclerotic plaque formation in the segment proximal to the bridged segment and the shielding of the bridged segment, Fig 4.

FIGURE 4: Pathophysiology of plaque formation proximal to bridged segment

Myocardial bridging was shown to occur in 16.1% individuals in a large scale Chinese study on coronary angiography. The main factors influencing the angiographic appearance are the intra-myocardial segment's length and thickness, the artery and muscle fiber alignment, and the type of tissue involved between them [17–19].

CONCLUSION:

The multidetector cardiac CT of myocardial bridging in our population with chest pain syndromes was 15.7%, with mid-LAD being the most common segment involved. It is crucial to determine the correlation between the of myocardial bridging and atherosclerotic coronary artery disease because prompt, aggressive treatment of the condition would cease its progression and provide symptomatic relief to patients.

DECLARATIONS:

Ethical Approval and Consent to participate:

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal.

Consent for publication:

I give my consent for the publication of identifiable details, which can include images and/or case history and/or details within the text to be published in this Journal

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